

ABSTRACT

In this review, The Prospects and Challenges of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprise in Tandag City under the new typical look at the effect of the pandemic (COVID-19) on MSMEs, the researcher conducted a survey on the level of Enterprises. A mixed-method examination strategies was utilized, that advances the systematic integration of Quantitative research design supported with Qualitative data to sustain the inquiry of the study. The quantitative and subjective researcher-made questionnaire was used to overview assessments of the impacts. It outlined that the triangulation strategy was picked as it allowed an opportunity for the researcher to get a total comprehension of the individuals' experiences. A focused group discussion was utilized as optional information. A few subjects arose. In the first place, mass cutbacks and terminations had effectively happened—only half a month into the emergency. Second, the danger of conclusion was adversely connected with the normal length of the emergency, besides organizations had broadly shifting convictions about the logical span of COVID-19 related disturbances. Third, the numerous private ventures were monetarily delicate. The larger part of organizations intended to look for subsidy through the monetary foundation, but it was denied and neglected because of stricter interaction and proportion of monetary association. The researcher assessed take-up rates and business versatility impacts for advances were compared with accolade-based projects, inward control, and other business focus points that were written in the Business Continuity Plan – the yield of the review.

Keywords: *MSMEs, COVID-19, pandemic, business continuity plan, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

This study aimed to present the Business Prospects and Challenges of MSMEs' that demonstrated the relevance, role, and contributions to the new normal. Undeniably, the MSMEs' supports achieved sustainable growth and played a vital role in the nation's overall production networks. They were the core of economic growth and had a remarkable ability to fuel the economy. It likewise set out numerous new possessions, opened doors, an economy made esteem, different items given to administrations, advancement opportunity made abundance for countries and growing expense based and built the opposition among the companions, and warmed up the market situation. Unfortunately, MSMEs' were being hit hard by the fall-out of the pandemic. For the economy, the COVID-19 was a rare and unexpected incident that carried potentially bear-sized social and economic impacts. The solutions were needed to give them the support in order to survive and continued their business to contribute to the global economy. This examination meant to have and built up a business continuity plan for MSMEs' that assisted with improving their profitability and guarantee better odds of endurance by turning out to be more aggressive in light of the fact that nothing on the MSMEs' might have arranged for the hard-hit they got from the pandemic emergency.

The researcher explored the gap, examined, and discovered new things about the Prospects and Challenges of the MSMEs'. Pandemic had stopped the movement in the areas of MSMEs and had been cruelly disturbed bringing about insolvencies, work misfortunes, and shutting of organizations, probably causing significant economic pressure in the open country and surprisingly around the world. The researcher's interest was to create a framework of a business continuity plan that raised and addressed the impact of the COVID-19 crisis brought on MSMEs. The yield of the investigation, help, and support strategy was essential for MSMEs. It gave insights, guidance, and resources for MSMEs' and supports organizations and policymakers.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. The researcher considered the utilization of mixed-method examination strategies of Quantitative supported with Qualitative data to sustain the inquiry of the study. A subjective report involves assorting information utilizing perception altogether for the researcher to comprehend a specific marvel. The quantitative elucidating and subjective researcher-made questionnaire was applied to overview assessments of the impacts of COVID-19 in the MSMEs'. This examination looks to discover answers to inquiries through the investigation of variable connections.

Participants/Respondents. This investigation investigates the most current information gathered at the Department of Trade and Industry – Tandag City-Provincial Office, and cross-checks the City Treasurer's Office, Identified Barangays with MSMEs' to get the general dependability and quality information. The MSMEs' organizations are sorted by the kind of business undertaking, size of the business, geographic area, and kind of industry. Creativities of the business are order dependent on resource size by the MSMEs'. In taking a gander at the Prospects and Challenges of these organizations, their ways of dealing with stress intend to address the significant imperatives that influence MSMEs' to turn off events.

Data Collection Procedure. A quantitative examination approach served as the primary data of this study involves gathering information from respondents of the study through overviews. Likewise alluded to as triangulation configuration utilizes more than one technique, the strategy for the study includes the utilization of both quantitative and supported with the qualitative questionnaire method served. This expressed that the strategy is the best as it helps at the end of the shortcomings of either subjective or quantitative strategies. A (FGD) focus group discussion was employed as secondary data in this research. It includes gathering 3 representatives each from Micro, Small, and Medium undertaking individuals from comparative foundations or encounters together to discuss the explicit subjects of interest. (Behar, 1996) portrayed an up close and personal connection that improves social reality. The examination process is a semi-organized meeting by the enterprise or a focus group discussion by the enterprise due to the current situation and compliance and health protocols must strictly be observed. It is a good way to gather respondents from similar backgrounds or experiences to discuss a specific topic of the MSMEs in relation to the Prospect's Challenges and interests to address the inquiries of the investigation. Quantitative were tabulated for this statistical treatment after the necessary data were acquired utilizing a researcher-made questionnaire that underwent the procedure and questionnaire validation by the accredited expert panel enough in the business and with the practical abilities in wording to approve the research instruments. The Likert scale is used to interpret the extent to which the Business Prospects and Challenges of MSMEs in Tandag City are under the new normal. The range and interpretation of the five-point scale. Likewise, supported by Qualitative data using FGD for triangulation.

Data Analysis Procedure. The primary data was accompanying statistical tool utilized to answer the issues in the review including the Pearson correlation test, a solid technique for recognizing and deciding how changes in the independent variable factor are related to the progressions in the dependent variable. These, permit the researcher to unquestionably figure out which components matter most and which variables can be disregarded and how these elements impact one another. Another is Kruskal-Wallis since the data is non-normal and to decide whether there is a significant difference between the factors. This is to decide the null hypothesis. In this study, the search approach is limited to, reviewed and published literature, books, journal articles, and research conference papers produced from internet databases. The primary objective of the literature review is to expand on the fundamental speculations on the feasible development of MSMEs., identify emerging theories, highlight key needs and, contribute to the building of sustainable growth of the MSME school of thought.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Prospects and Opportunities are specific pointers that MSMEs' have to bring to offer. This business opportunity is the initiator of an undertaking and it comprises of a progression of conditions in the market that enable transforming a business thought into a business venture.

A similar technique was utilized to gather the information and adequately present the outcomes utilizing the Likert scale with 5 concentrations to decipher the information. On the information introduced in this table, the degree of the Business Prospects or Opportunities by the MSMEs', which essentially implies that a greater part of respondents from the three degrees of MSMEs' endeavors are deciphered dependent on their discernments and that it is very imported. An extremely high or OK reaction made by the respondent with respect to the information that is being asked in the quantitative survey and ensuring that each significant issue is being talked about. Statistically, information is introduced in the table with the normal reaction pace of 4.59 which is similar to the significance of the study results. Which basically thought to be superb in most conditions. The examination is driven by undeniable degrees of inspiration to finish the review.

The researcher comes up with the measurably result that the MSMEs ensure prudent usage and creation plans" irrefutably, in light of the information show the pertinence, job, and commitments

of Micro-, Small-and Medium-Enterprises (MSMEs'). This essentially implies Fostering the development and MSMEs are in this way key to the comprehensive development of urban areas and in making work for urban tenants, including minimized gatherings like migrants from a poor rural location. MSMEs play an important role in the wider ecosystem of firms. Start-ups and young firms, which are generally small or micro firms, are the primary source of net job creation in many countries and are the driving force of innovation and sustainability in the private sector.

Another is advanced financial consideration and have the potential to regenerate under-served geographic areas and MSMEs provide incomes to helpless families, women, and youth through employment and entrepreneurship opportunities with the average response of 4.71 connotes that MSMEs are huge in light of the fact that they assist with decreasing neediness by making occupations for the nation's developing workforce. According to the journal posted by <http://legacy.senate.gov.ph>, they stimulate economic development in rural and far-flung areas. They serve as valuable partners to large enterprises as suppliers and providers of support services. They serve as the breeding grounds for new entrepreneurs and large corporations. A vibrant MSMEs sector is thus an indication of a thriving and growing economy. Despite policies that aim to provide an enabling environment for MSMEs' development, the sector still faces various constraints that prevent it from realizing its full growth and potential. The Implementing Rules and Regulations of Section 4 (AA) of the Bayanihan to Heal as One Act (Republic Act No. 11469) require covered institutions to implement a minimum 30-day grace period for loans due during the quarantine period. It requires lenders not to impose interest on fees and other charges to future payments or amortizations of individuals, households, MSMEs', and corporate borrowers. No additional documentary stamp tax (DST) will be imposed as a consequence of this relief granted. Bayanihan to Recover as One Act ensures, among others, that credit accommodations for MSMEs be imposed a low interest, payable within three years with no collateral required if the loan does not exceed P3 million. It likewise directs the Small Business Corp. to expand its loan programs for MSMEs' by increasing available loanable funds, reducing eligibility requirements, increasing maximum loan amounts per borrower, reducing interest rates, and extending loan terms. A standby fund is also being set for appropriation to support the activities of the MSME sector.

In the statement made by Secretary of (DTI) Department of Trade and Industry Ramon M. Lopez, In the administration's 10-point socio-economic agenda which aims to broaden the gains of economic development, address inequality, and uplift the quality of life of all Filipinos, President Rodrigo Duterte envisioned the reduction of poverty from 21.6% in 2015 to 13%-15% by 2022. The Department of Trade and Industry is one with the President's desire to achieve inclusive growth and bring shared prosperity for all by empowering our MSMEs', which form a significant part of our country's growth resurgence. In his foreword, President Rodrigo R. Duterte stated that the MSME Development Plan 2017-2022 will ensure the further empowerment of rising entrepreneurs in the next five years through development strategies that will create globally competitive MSMEs' that are regionally integrated, resilient, sustainable, and innovative.

As per the OECD, development is characterized as the presentation of a new or fundamentally further developed item or the execution of a new process, an organizational technique in strategic policies, and adaptation of this business continuity plan. (OECD, 2005). Every organization has components of foundation, values, leadership, abilities, culture, and cycles (Popli et al., 2016), and the test is to adjust these parts to an advancement structure that is viable to the organization and its targets (Skarzynski et al., 2013). The production of a suitable organizational culture that energizes correspondence and information sharing will make it accessible for use by the whole business organization (Woodfield et al., 2017). Information to adapt to changes from the view of prospects and challenges is one of the primary wellsprings of development and the making of an upper hand for any business (Weijs-Perrée et al., 2019). Nonetheless, presenting a business with new outside information isn't adequate for development (Jansen et al., 2005). To utilize the new information really, a business should foster properly organized processes that will make it conceivable to incorporate it into the current information (Björk et al., 2010).

Table 1. Extent of the following Business Prospects or Opportunities assisting the operation of the MSMEs

Prospects or Opportunity by the MSMEs'	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
MSMEs guarantee economical utilization and creation designs.	4.73	Very High Prospects
MSMEs can contribute to the adaptation of economic activities/sectors.	4.66	Very High Prospects
MSMEs have the potential for advancing great administration principles and standards.	4.67	Very High Prospects
MSMEs advance development. New and small firms are often the driving force behind the innovations that are significant for economic growth.	4.67	Very High Prospects
MSMEs advance financial consideration and have the potential to regenerate under-served geographic areas.	4.71	Very High Prospects
MSMEs provide incomes to low income and marginalized groups.	4.61	Very High Prospects
MSMEs have a role in conflict/savagery avoidance.	4.39	Very High Prospects
MSMEs provide incomes to helpless families, women and youth through employment and entrepreneurship opportunities.	4.71	Very High Prospects
MSMEs' Strengthen the method for execution and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development.	4.64	Very High Prospects
MSMEs' Adopting ethical business practices and norms and advance the combination of these guidelines inside esteem chains for their development and benefit.	4.65	Very High Prospects
MSME entrepreneurs could do to prevent negative environmental impacts.	4.65	Very High Prospects
MSMEs guarantee feasible utilization and creation designs.	4.48	Very High Prospects
MSME business visionaries could never have really bad natural effects.	4.36	Very High Prospects
MSMEs accomplish sexual orientation uniformity and engage all ladies and young ladies.	4.34	Very High Prospects
TOTAL	4.59	Very High Prospects

The verbal interpretation of the descriptors for response options determines the validity of the questions. It also determined whether their level of consideration in deciding this factor significantly on the following:

Descriptor	Rating	Mean Range
No Prospects at all	1	1.00 – 1.79
Low Prospects	2	1.80 – 2.59
Moderate Prospects	3	2.60 – 3.39
High Prospects	4	3.40 – 4.19
Very High Prospects	5	4.20 – 5.00

Very High Prospects. Expressing a solid opportunity for MSMEs' headway or progress.

High Prospects. -Alluded to as possible and achieve the business opportunity having a significant level of possibilities.

Moderate Prospects. A minimum level of acknowledgment of some openings brought by MSMEs'.

Low Prospects. It infers little assumption for specific freedoms from MSMEs'.

NO prospects at all. Described as unimportant, no clear an open door later on.

Table 2 presents the Degree of Challenges faced by Micro Small and Medium Enterprises in Tandag City dependent on the reactions made by the 89 respondents of three levels of MSMEs' Enterprise with a total response rate of 4.41 average mean range. In the 1st position Decrease in Revenue with a 4.65 reaction rate, in the 2nd position is the Liquidity Problems with a reaction pace of 4.58 and in the 3rd position isn't as much as Bankruptcy with a normal reaction pace of 4.57. A large portion of the MSMEs' was embraced to feature the issues looking at their mission to get bank credit (advances) from monetary establishments to attempt different exercises. All together MSMEs' to keep on satisfying the above mentioned and considerably more, they need admittance to fund to do their business activity and development. The appearing absence of money for MSMEs' isn't just impeding their development yet additionally the development of the country's economy. Most business visionaries opt for non-payment due to the liquidity issue, A decline in income is terrible for a business, the main situation where an abatement in income isn't harming a business is when expenses are additionally diminishing. During this pandemic, the Economic conditions power customers to save on optional buys. A business is in danger of not making back the initial investment or having extremely low edges of security and levels of benefit.

Once more, according to an economic perspective, be that as it may, endeavors are providers, yet in addition customers; this assumes a significant part in case they are to situate themselves in a market with buying power: their demand for industrial or consumer goods will invigorate the movement of their providers, similarly as their own action is animated by the demand of their customers. In view of the perennial financing challenge faced by these SMEs', many interventions have been made by the government through its recent monetary policy and financial sector reforms. These have substantially increased other financial lending to the private sector but limited access to credit, high-interest rates, and prohibitive collateral requirements still pose significant constraints to the growth of many MSMEs'. Access to medium to long-term financing necessary for capital investment is still tight.

Utilizing different sorts of business continuity plan and business systems empower MSMEs to turn out to be important for the advancement scene (Bigliardi et al, 2018) in light of the fact that main MSMEs have adequate capacity to deal with the whole business development process autonomously, and they need to team up with different substances.

Table 2. Degree of the following Challenges or Threats faced by the MSMEs

Challenges faced by the MSMEs in general.	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Inadequate working capital	4.53	Very High Threat
Decrease in Revenue	4.65	Very High Threat
Stiff competition from larger companies	4.43	Very High Threat
Employment Turnover	4.37	Very High Threat
Difficulties in sourcing raw materials	4.51	Very High Threat
Liquidity Problems	4.58	Very High Threat
Low-capacity utilization	4.46	Very High Threat
Bankruptcy	4.57	Very High Threat
Lack of management skills & strategies	4.35	Very High Threat
Succession Planning	4.30	Very High Threat
Poor educational background of operators	4.38	Very High Threat
Lack of Innovation	4.56	Very High Threat
Undeveloped Sales Channels	4.31	Very High Threat
Poor Infrastructure	4.37	Very High Threat
Insufficient use of Information Technology	4.26	Very High Threat
Establishing a work from home – scheme	4.35	Very High Threat
Productivity	4.54	Very High Threat
Systems and processes	4.28	Very High Threat
Measuring Performance	4.19	High Threat
Leadership and Culture	4.17	High Threat
Making Business Stand Out	4.54	Very High Threat
TOTAL	4.41	Very High Threat

The verbal interpretation of the descriptors for response options determines the validity of the questions. It also determined whether their level of consideration in deciding this factor significantly on the following:

Very High Threat - expressing or recommending a danger of mischief, risk, and so on. It is an exceptionally high factor that can carry mishaps or harm to a business.

High Threat - prone to bring about a business disappointment and having a significant degree of dangers.

Moderate Threat - keeping inside sensible or appropriate cutoff points; it isn't extreme, or serious.

Low Threat - not prone to bring about disappointment or not having a significant of dangers.

NO Threat at all - characterized as insignificant, uninterested, or lacking sign to stress over.

Table 3 shows the significant relationship between the prospects and challenges in terms of the difference in the decision-making of MSMEs' entrepreneurs as the showed a result with a p-value equal to 0.694. This implies there is a significant relationship between the two factors. These are choices taken by MSMEs business visionaries from the accessible choices as introduced in the information. It implies that MSMEs must responsively tackle choice issues, however, should likewise proactively seek after choices regarding what open doors. Each developing business truly faces a scope of many difficulties. As the MSMEs business develops, there are various issues and open doors that request various arrangements.

MSMEs organizations that were characterized by the authority as fundamental for proceeding with economic conduct were permitted to proceed with their business activities under new ordinary limitations. However, it is unimaginable that the way that things would have gone had the advancements at present being used by organizations during this pandemic not been as inescapable. (Akpan et al., 2020b). Business prospects and challenges for MSMEs in Tandag City are really felt not just local but worldwide.

Directly following this Covid19 emergency and to keep away from the closure of economic activities, the utilization of certain innovations that were not viewed as fundamental by MSMEs ventures became essential to keep away from a total closure of the worldwide economy (Ting et al., 2020).

Table 3. The significant relationship between the prospects and challenges in terms of decision-making to continue or discontinue the business operation?

		Correlation	p-value	Conclusion
Prospects	Challenges	0.694	0.000	There is a significant correlation

The information shows the critical distinction between challenges looked at by MSMEs and the possibilities or openings presented by MSMEs came about with p esteem equivalents to 0.000 which is lesser than the alpha worth of 0.05. This means there is a significant difference between the two variables. MSME challenges some are steady and others are especially significant. For instance the difficulties in utilizing the two measures for functionally characterizing MSMEs, in particular, business and resource size.

Table 4. The significant difference in the view of the Respondents on the Challenges brought by COVID19 on Micro Small Medium Entrepreneurs?

	Mean	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Micro	4.36	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis	There is a significant difference between the 3 groups of MSMEs'.
Small	4.81			
Medium	5.00			

CONCLUSION

This research analyzed the business prospects and challenges of MSMEs among 89 business people in Tandag City. The consequences of this study showed that there are various attributes of undertakings including decisions conveying the opportunities and threats of the business enterprises.

Navigation altogether affected the decision-production of business visionaries, shows that in business Prospects or Opportunities the vast majority of the MSMEs truly need to ensure affordable use and creation plans this refereeing to advancement. This advancement assists MSMEs with working on their efficiency and producing better items in the market in the midst of pandemics. Generally, upgrading their competitiveness in the new normal and the undeniably requesting and fast-paced global market. Business visionaries incorporate the internal and external data that impact them to make their decision. In Barron's view (2004) business people's data level in an obscure and new condition impacts their pursuing choices which accord with the consequence of this review. To summarize, assuming business people approach the right and valuable data, they can pick the best choice and better exhibition in the performance of the MSMEs.

There's no question that the COVID-19 pandemic has added MSMEs challenges in Tandag City, paying little heed to measure, area, or financing. The monetary delicacy of numerous private companies, and what profoundly meant they are by the ongoing emergency. As indicated by Eggers (2020), the majority of the investigations that attention to finance is worried about the outcomes of the emergency on MSMEs, to be specific, the absence of subsidizing and supporting sources.

The business continuity plan is a significant composing technique of strategy that alludes to the perseverance and flexibility philosophies of MSMEs during the new normal. Each business needs a business continuity plan, there is a requirement for strategies and instruments that put the micro and small enterprises to make practice this business continuity plan not just for medium ventures. It sets out how you will plan for a pandemic and keep on working after the new normal. It will assist with limiting recuperation time and decrease your business misfortunes.

The researcher firmly suggests that MSMEs ought to consider the utilization of a business continuity plan as their supportive emergency the board methodologies in the drawn-out run, zeroing in on monetary elements as well as completely considering non-monetary variables, proprietors' top management, as well as various degrees of the workforce, ought to be engaged with creating crisis management mechanisms in the new normal.

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